

Daryna Brahar

Student

Bukovinian State Medical University

Chernivtsi, Ukraine

Inna Vlaiko

Student

Bukovinian State Medical University

Chernivtsi, Ukraine

Andruschak Margarita*Candidate of Medical Sciences, Associate Professor of the Department of Infectious Diseases and Epidemiology*

Bukovinian State Medical University

Chernivtsi, Ukraine

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13969432>**INFLAMMATORY BOWEL DISEASES AND COURSE OF COVID-19****Abstract.**

COVID-19 pandemic is one of the largest pandemics of this century that humanity has faced in 2020. This pandemic pose a challenge for whole world. Coronavirus disease (COVID-19) is infectious disease caused by Sars-CoV-2 virus [1]. This virus can affect to the immune system: viral entry by angiotensin-converting enzyme-2 receptor and an excessive activation of the immune system are key to understanding both incidence and severity of the disease [2]. Coronavirus disease triggered few various pathologies and caused the exacerbation of chronic diseases.

Inflammatory bowel diseases include ulcerative colitis and Chron's disease. IBD diseases are conditions associated with inordinate response of immune system.

Thus, IBD has been postulated to change risk or course of COVID-19.

Aim: *incidence and severity of COVID-19 in patients with inflammatory bowel diseases*

Materials and methods: *a review of current evidence.*

Keywords: *Covid-19, inflammatory bowel diseases, ulcerative colitis, Chron's disease*

Results. In recent years, the number of studies of on connection between COVID-19 and IBD has increased. Latest evidences confirm the severity of COVID-19 based on overaction of the immune system. From this follows the hypothesis that the course of COVID-19 depends on the presence of inflammatory bowel diseases.

In propensity-matched research network analysis by Hadi Y et al. databases were from TriNetX. Clinical and laboratory results were analyzed between patients with COVID-19 with and without previous IBD diagnosis. A total of 4310 patients with IBD with a diagnosis of COVID-19 were identified, and a total of 851 163 patients with no history of IBD who were diagnosed with COVID-19 in the study period were included in the control group.

In the analysis, a higher risk for hospitalisation and need for critical care was observed in the IBD cohort compared to patients without IBD. Additionally, patients with IBD had to were at higher risk of hospital treatment. Patients in the IBD cohort on corticosteroids at baseline were found to be at increased risk for hospitalization and critical care compared to the non-IBD population. Less than $\leq 3\%$ required mechanical ventilation, critical care or died during the 30-days post-diagnosis period. [3]

In the rapid review and meta-analysis carried out by Muhammad Aziz et al. databases were used from:

PubMed/Medline, Embase, Cochrane, Web of Science, LitCOVID NIH and WHO regarding COVID-19. A total of 9177 patients with IBD were diagnosed of COVID-19 in 151 patients. In the series of patients with IBD and COVID-19 a hospitalization rate more than 40% was obtained. The rate of patients, who need a mechanical ventilation of 10.7% and a mortality of 6.4%. This percentage may be overestimated because the databases at the beginning of COVID-19 were at a low level and different mortality reported be countries.[4]

In the analysis by Alloca et al.,databases from 12 European countries included 23,879 patients with IBD. 97 patients with IBD and associated COVID-19: a hospitalization rate of 24%, a pneumonia rate of 22%, a mortality of 1%. [5]

In the case-control study of Lukin et al., a total of 240 patients: 80 patients with IBD and 160 patients without previous IBD diagnosis. Databases from New York hospital. Rates of hospitalization, intubation or death were analyzed in both groups: 23.5% in IBD patients and 35.3% in patients without IBD. [6]

In the population-based cohort study by JonasF.Ludvigsson et al., databases from the nationwide registers in Sweden included 67 292 patients with IBD. Results: 179 (0.27%) IBD patients and 500 (0.17%) general population controls were admitted to hospital with COVID-19. The equivalent numbers for severe COVID-19 were 65 (0.1%) and 183 (0.06%). In this

population-based cohort study of patients with IBD, was found a partially increased risk of hospitalization but no increased risk of severe course of COVID-19. [7]

In the analysis by S. Singh et al. databases were used from TriNetX. A cohort included 196 403 patients with IBD 1901 patients were tested for COVID-19, and a total of 232 patients with IBD were diagnosed with COVID-19. During the same time period, 19776 patients without IBD were also diagnosed with COVID-19. In a crude analysis, there was no difference in the risk of severe COVID-19 between the patients with IBD and the patients without IBD. The risk of a severe course of COVID-19 was related. Patients with IBD, who had severe COVID-19, were older and had comorbidities. The outcome of hospitalization or mortality after COVID-19 in patients with IBD is similar to patients without IBD. In addition, patients with IBD with COVID-19 on long-term biologics or non-steroid immunomodulatory therapies did not have a higher risk of poor COVID-19 outcomes. The risk for severe COVID-19 in patients with IBD is also similar to the common risk factors for COVID-19. [8]

In the analysis by Ungaro RC et al. databases were used from the international registry. A cohort included 1439 patients from 47 countries of whom 7.8% had severe COVID-19 with most being age 50 years and older. [9]

Conclusions. The severity of the course of COVID-19 is affected by comorbidities. However, from these data patients with IBD and patients without IBD have a similar risk to incidence of COVID-19 and do not have a higher risk of severe COVID-19.

Instead, immunosuppressive and biological therapies used in the treatment of inflammatory bowel diseases can increase the risk of disease. However, these therapies also have a positive effect: they block the cytokine storm, thereby decreasing the severity of COVID-19. [10]

These data support to continuation of effective steroid, non-steroid and biological therapies to minimize active disease and decrease a severe COVID-19.

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